

Podatki za primerjavo rezultatov ekstenzivnega in intenzivnega terenskega pregleda na avtocestah Slovenije (Podatkovni članek)

Data for comparing the results of extensive and intensive field surveys on Slovenian motorways (Data paper)

© Luka Gruškovnjak

Univerza v Ljubljani, Filozofska fakulteta, Oddelek za arheologijo, Center za interdisciplinarne raziskave v arheologiji (CIRA); luka.gruskovnjak@ff.uni-lj.si

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Izveček: Prispevek predstavlja podatkovno zbirko, namenjeno primerjavi med rezultati ekstenzivnega in intenzivnega terenskega pregleda na avtocestah Slovenije, katere cilj je bil ovrednotenje učinkovitosti metodologije pregledov. Zbirka podatkov je bila ustvarjena s prostorsko primerjavo rezultatov ekstenzivnih in intenzivnih pregledov na avtocestah Slovenije. Skupno obsega podatke o 258 intenzivno pregledanih lokacijah, med katerimi je 19 takih, ki se ne prekrivajo z območji ekstenzivnega pregleda, in 232 takih, ki se s temi območji prekrivajo in so tako primerne za primerjavo med obema fazama oz. strategijama pregleda. Posamezne lokacije so predstavljene v tabelah, ki vsebujejo podatke o številu odkritih najdb posameznega obdobja: o velikosti ekstenzivno in intenzivno pregledanih površin, o razmerjih med velikostjo ekstenzivno in intenzivno ter površinsko in podpovršinsko pregledanih površin, o gostotah posameznih vrst gradiva, odkritih s površinskim in podpovršinskim pregledom, o razmerjih med gostoto posameznih vrst gradiva, odkritih v ekstenzivni in intenzivni fazi, ter o regionalizaciji lokacij. Poleg tega podatkovna zbirka vsebuje besedilo s podporno analizo primerjave rezultatov ekstenzivne in intenzivne faze pregledov, ki ni bila vključena v povezani izvorni znanstveni članek. Podatkovna zbirka je shranjena v Repozitoriju Univerze v Ljubljani ter omogoča ponovno rabo v obliki preverjanja predstavljenih rezultatov analize ali izvajanja nadaljnjih analiz na predstavljenem nizu podatkov.

Ključne besede: arheološka metodologija, arheološki terenski pregled, površinski pregled, podpovršinski pregled, avtoceste Slovenije

Ozadje

Podatkovna zbirka je nastala v okviru doktorske raziskave ovrednotenja učinkovitosti metodologije arheoloških terenskih pregledov v specifičnih okoljskih in kulturnih pogojih Slovenije (Gruškovnjak 2022a). Del raziskave je obravnaval vprašanje vpliva metod in tehnik pregleda ter gostote gradiva na odkrivanje najdišč s terenskimi pregledi. V okviru tega je nastala pričujoča zbirka, ki jo sestavljajo podatki, pridobljeni s prostorsko primerjavo rezultatov ekstenzivnih in intenzivnih pregledov na avtocestah Slovenije. Terenske raziskave so potekale med letoma 1994 in 2009 v okviru projekta izgradnje sloven-

Abstract: The article presents a database designed to compare the results of extensive and intensive field surveys on Slovenian motorways, with the aim of evaluating the effectiveness of the survey methodology. The database was created through a spatial comparison of the results of extensive and intensive surveys on Slovenian motorways. It contains data from 258 intensively surveyed locations, of which 19 do not overlap with areas covered by extensive survey, while 232 do overlap and are therefore suitable for comparison between the two phases or survey strategies. Individual locations are presented in tables containing data on the number of finds recorded in each period; the size of extensively and intensively surveyed areas; the ratios between the sizes of extensively and intensively surveyed areas and surface and subsurface surveyed areas; the densities of individual types of material identified through surface and subsurface surveys; the ratios between the densities of individual types of material recorded in the extensive and intensive phases; and the regionalisation of locations. In addition, the database includes text with supporting analysis comparing the results of the extensive and intensive phases of the surveys, which was not included in the related original scientific paper. The database is stored in the Repository of the University of Ljubljana. It allows reuse by verifying the presented analysis results or further analysing the given dataset.

Keywords: archaeological methodology, archaeological field survey, surface survey, subsurface survey, Slovenian motorways

skih avtocest, največjega razvojnega projekta v Sloveniji doslej (glej Djurić 2003). Površinski in podpovršinski terenski pregled sta bila v okviru projekta uporabljena kot glavni metodi za odkrivanje še neznanih arheoloških najdišč, ki so domnevno ležala na območju gradbenih posegov.

Raziskava je na eni strani izhajala iz ugotovitve, da na učinkovitost odkrivanja najdišč s terenskimi pregledi vplivajo raznovrstni dejavniki, med katere sodijo tudi lastnosti arheološkega gradiva in uporabljena metodologija njegovega odkrivanja (Gruškovnjak 2017a; 2019; Gruškovnjak, Tiefengraber, Črešnar 2019), na drugi strani

pa iz ugotovitve, da lahko podatki intenzivno pregledanih območij služijo za ovrednotenje učinkovitosti manj intenzivnih strategij pregleda (Burger *et al.* 2004; Burger, Todd 2006, 241–243; Burger, Todd, Burnett 2008, 217–221; glej tudi Banning *et al.* 2017). V okviru avtocestnega projekta so namreč pregledi potekali v dveh fazah – ekstenzivni in intenzivni –, ki se razlikujeta glede na intenzivnost pregleda.

V podatkovnem članku predstavljamo podatke, pridobljene s primerjavo prostorskega prekrivanja obeh faz pregleda, ki so bili namenjeni analizi vpliva gostote gradiva v zgornjem delu tal in metodologije njegovega odkrivanja, specifično intenzivnost pregleda (ekstenzivni in intenzivni) ter metodo pregleda (površinski in podpovršinski). Rezultati analize so predstavljeni v izvirnem znanstvenem članku (Gruškovnjak 2025b), ki ga dopolnjuje pričujoči podatkovni članek, v katerem je natančneje predstavljena v analizi uporabljena podatkovna zbirka.

Slika 1. Karta s primerom načina primerjave prekrivanja mrež ekstenzivnega (ETP) in intenzivnega (ITP) pregleda na najdišču Ivanka. Intenzivni pregled je razdeljen na štiri območja (I–IV). Območje IV se ne prekriva z mrežo ekstenzivnega pregleda, zato je izključeno iz primerjave. Območje I, ki predstavlja samostojno zaključeno mrežo, je obravnavano kot samostojna lokacija prekrivanja, imenovana Ivanka I. Ta se deloma prekriva s tremi zbiralnimi enotami ekstenzivnega pregleda, poudarjenimi s svetlomodro. V primerjavo je vključena celotna mreža območja I in vse prečnice teh treh zbiralnih enot. Območji II in III se stikata, zato sta združeni v eno lokacijo, imenovano Ivanka II–III, ki se le deloma prekriva z mrežo ekstenzivnega pregleda. Lokacijo smo v celoti primerjali z zbiralnimi enotami ekstenzivnega pregleda, poudarjenimi s svetlomodro, s katerimi se prekriva. Odločanje o zbiralnih enotah, ki bodo vključene v primerjavo, je bilo na vseh obravnavanih lokacijah intenzivnega pregleda na avtocestah Slovenije sorodno predstavljenemu primeru. Vendar pa je bilo treba zaradi zelo raznolikih načinov prekrivanja mrež na vsaki lokaciji sprejeti zanjo specifično odločitev o tem, kaj vključiti v primerjavo.

Figure 1. Map showing an example of how overlap between extensive (EFS) and intensive (IFS) survey grids was compared at the Ivanka site. The intensive survey is divided into four areas (I–IV). Area IV does not overlap with the extensive survey grid and is therefore excluded from the comparison. Area I, which represents a separate closed grid, is treated as a separate overlap location called Ivanka I. It partially overlaps with three collection units of the extensive survey, highlighted in light blue. The entire network of Area I and all transects of these three collection units are included in the comparison. Areas II and III are adjacent and are therefore combined into a single location called Ivanka II–III, which only partially overlaps with the extensive survey grid. The location is fully compared with the extensive survey collection units highlighted in light blue, with which it overlaps. The selection of collection units for comparison followed the same principles applied at all intensive survey locations on Slovenian motorways. However, due to the highly variable grid-overlap situations, specific decisions regarding inclusion were required at each location.

Zbirka vključuje tabelarično predstavljene podatke o lokacijah prekrivanja obeh faz pregleda, vključno s podatki o velikosti pregledanih območij, številu odkritih najdb, gostoti odkritih najdb in drugih, v analizi opazovanih parametrov.

Geografski obseg: Slovenija, Slovenske gorice, Podravje, Celjska kotlina, Ljubljanska kotlina, Dinarska podolja in ravniki, Vipavska dolina, Slovenska Istra.

Obdobja: prazgodovina, rimsko obdobje, zgodnji srednji vek, novi vek (gradivo terenskih pregledov ni natančneje časovno opredeljeno).

Metodologija

V okviru avtocestnega projekta je bila metoda površinskega pregleda uporabljena na neporaščenih obdelovalnih površinah, metoda podpovršinskega pregleda pa na poraščenih neobdelanih površinah. Terenske raziskave so bile izvedene v dveh fazah, ekstenzivni in intenzivni, ki se med seboj razlikujeta v tehniki in predvsem strategiji izvedbe pregleda. Pri tem se tehnika nanaša na način izvedbe metode pregleda, strategija pa na prostorsko razporeditev izvajanja tehnike (glej Gruškovnjak 2017b, 116, op. 50).

Slika 2. Primerjava števila lokacij intenzivnega pregleda (ITP lokacije) po pokrajinah. Primerjava vključuje vse ITP lokacije, ki se prostorsko prekrivajo z ekstenzivno fazo pregleda, ter tiste, ki se prostorsko ne prekrivajo, ob tem pa prikazuje tudi število lokacij, določenih na podlagi ekstenzivnega pregleda (ETP lokacije).

Figure 2. Comparison of the number of intensive survey locations (IFS locations) by region. The comparison includes all IFS locations that overlap spatially with the extensive survey phase, as well as those that do not, and also shows the number of locations identified on the basis of the extensive survey (EFS locations).

Ekstenzivna faza je zajela celotno območje trase avtocest in drugih povezanih objektov. Strategijo pregleda je predstavljala raba zbiralnih enot, razdeljenih na 50 m dolge prečnice v medsebojnem razmiku 10 m (slika 1; glej Gruškovnjak 2024a–b). Pri metodi površinskega pregleda je bila uporabljena tehnika hoje po prečnicah in zbiranja vseh zaznanih površinskih najdb v širini približno enega metra v liniji hoje, pri metodi podpovršinskega pregleda pa izkop po ene testne jame velikosti $40 \times 40 \times 40$ cm na vsaki prečnici in zbiranje najdb v njej.

Območja s pozitivnimi rezultati so bila kot potencialna arheološka najdišča podvržena naslednji fazi intenzivnih pregledov. Strategijo pregleda je predstavljala raba mreže kvadrantov 10×10 m (slika 1; glej Gruškovnjak 2024a–b). Pri metodi površinskega pregleda je bila uporabljena tehnika pregledovanja celotne površine vsakega kvadranta, pri podpovršinskem pregledu pa je bila izkopana po ena testna jama velikosti $40 \times 40 \times 40$ cm v vsakem kvadrantu (Djurić 2003, 16–18).

Rezultati ekstenzivnih in intenzivnih pregledov so bili nato obdelani v geografskem informacijskem sistemu.¹ Pri tem žal ne razpolagamo s podatki o vseh lokacijah, na katerih je bil izveden intenzivni pregled, na eni strani zaradi nedostopnosti nekaterih poročil ali nepopolnih podatkov v poročilih, na drugi strani pa zaradi časovne omejitve, ki ni omogočala pridobitve in digitalizacije podatkov za vse obstoječe lokacije. Skupno so bili digitalizirani rezultati za 251 lokacij, na katerih je bil izveden intenzivni pregled. Med njimi je 19 lokacij, na katerih se mreže obeh strategij pregleda ne prekrivajo.² S podatki o rezultatih obeh strategij pregleda, ki se prostorsko prekrivajo, tako razpolagamo na skupno 232 lokacijah.

Primerljivost podatkov

Pri tem je treba izpostaviti, da posamezne lokacije intenzivnega terenskega pregleda (odslej ITP lokacije) niso nujno istovetne posameznim lokacijam, določenim na podlagi ekstenzivnega pregleda. Nekatere so bile zaradi svoje velikosti pregledane z več prostorsko ločenimi

¹ Objava podatkovne baze z vsemi rezultati pregledov obeh faz je v pripravi.

² Razlogi za to so različni. Nekatere lokacije so že znana arheološka območja, na katerih potrebe po intenzivni fazi ni bilo, nekatere so območja razširitve gradbenih posegov, ki v času izvedbe ekstenzivne faze niso bili predvideni ali znani, nekatere pa območja, kjer je intenzivna faza pregleda zgrešila območje, pregledano v ekstenzivni fazi.

Slika 3. A: Primerjava razmerja med primerjanimi površinami, pregledanimi z ekstenzivno (ETP) in intenzivno (ITP) strategijo pregleda. B: Razponi velikosti intenzivno pregledanih površin po lokacijah.

Figure 3. A: Comparison of the ratio between areas surveyed using extensive (EFS) and intensive (IFS) survey strategies. B: Size ranges of intensively surveyed areas by location.

mrežami intenzivnega pregleda, ki tako predstavljajo posamezne lokacije prekrivanja mrež obeh strategij pregleda. Vsaka izmed teh mrež je bila obravnavana kot samostojna lokacija prekrivanja, saj primerjava med obema fazama pregleda zahteva čim bolj zvezna in ozko

zamejena območja prekrivanja. Število ITP lokacij, s katerimi razpolagamo, je po posameznih pokrajinah (slika 2) zelo različno in ne ustreza številu lokacij, ki so bile v pokrajinah določene na podlagi rezultatov ekstenzivnega pregleda. Razlogov za to je lahko več: bodisi ker

Slika 4. A: Primerjava števila in deleža lokacij, ki so bile v ekstenzivni fazi (ETP) pregledane le s površinskim (P) ali podpovršinskim (PP) pregledom oz. z obema metodama (P/PP). V okviru teh je predstavljeno število lokacij, ki so bile v intenzivni fazi (ITP) pregledane z le eno metodo ali z obema metodama. B: Primerjava deleža lokacij, ki so bile v intenzivni fazi (ITP) pregledane le s površinskim (P) ali podpovršinskim (PP) pregledom oz. z obema metodama (P/PP), glede na to, ali so bile v ekstenzivni fazi (ETP) pregledane le z eno metodo ali z obema metodama.

Figure 4. A: Comparison of the number and percentage of sites that were surveyed in the extensive phase (EFS) using only surface (S) or subsurface (SS) surveys, or both methods (S/SS). Within this framework, the number of sites surveyed in the intensive phase (IFS) using only one method or both methods is presented. B: Comparison of the percentage of sites that were surveyed in the intensive phase (IFS) using only surface (S) or subsurface (SS) survey, or both methods (S/SS), according to whether they were surveyed in the extensive phase (EFS) using only one method or both methods.

Primerjava razmerja med površinsko in podpovršinsko pregledanimi površinami
Comparison of the ratio between surface and subsurface surveyed areas

digitalizacija podatkov ni bila mogoča, bodisi zaradi ne-prekrivanja z ekstenzivnim pregledom, bodisi zaradi razlik v določanju lokacij za potrebe primerjave rezultatov obeh faz pregleda.

Nadalje je treba izpostaviti, da je primerjava rezultatov obeh faz pregleda na lokacijah prekrivanja do določene mere neizogibno problematična. V skoraj nobenem primeru namreč ne gre za popolno in točno prekrivanje mrež obeh strategij. V primerjavo so vključene celotne zaključene mreže intenzivnega pregleda, ki se v celoti ali vsaj delno prekrivajo z mrežo ekstenzivnega pregleda, in zbiralne enote ekstenzivnega pregleda, s katerimi se se vsaj delno prekrivajo (slika 1). Mreže obeh strategij pregleda tako lahko pokrivajo tudi območje, ki ga druge ne. Velikostna razmerja med ekstenzivno in intenzivno pregledanimi površinami na posameznih lokacijah prekrivanja so tako lahko precej različna (slika 3: A). Večja kot so odstopanja v velikosti površine, bolj problematična je njihova primerjava. Najpogosteje pri celotni primerjani površini obeh strategij površina ekstenzivnega pregleda predstavlja 50–64 % in površina intenzivnega pregleda 36–50 %. Velike razlike so tudi v absolutni velikosti intenzivno pregledanih površin (slika 3: B) in posledično v primerjavo vključenih ekstenzivno pregledanih površin. Kvartilni razpon velikosti intenzivno pregledanih površin sega od 3.958 m² do 12.700 m² s sredinsko vrednostjo

Slika 5. A: Primerjava razmerja med v intenzivni fazi površinsko (ITP P) in podpovršinsko (ITP PP) pregledanimi površinami na lokacijah, ki so bile v ekstenzivni fazi pregledane izključno površinsko (ETP P). B: Primerjava razmerij med metodama na lokacijah, ki so bile v ekstenzivni fazi pregledane tako s površinskim (ETP P) kot podpovršinskim (ETP PP) pregledom. C: Primerjava razmerja med v intenzivni fazi površinsko (ITP P) in podpovršinsko (ITP PP) pregledanimi površinami na lokacijah, ki so bile v ekstenzivni fazi pregledane z uporabo obeh metod (ETP P/PP).

Figure 5. A: Comparison of the ratio between areas surveyed in the intensive phase using surface (IFS S) and subsurface (IFS SS) methods at locations that were surveyed exclusively with the surface method (EFS S) in the extensive phase. B: Comparison of the ratios between the methods at locations that were surveyed, both using surface (ETP P) and subsurface (ETP PP) methods, during the extensive phase. C: Comparison of the ratio between areas surveyed using surface (ITP P) and subsurface (ITP PP) methods in the intensive phase at locations that were surveyed using both methods (ETP P/PP) in the extensive phase.

7.000 m², medtem ko najmanjše intenzivno pregledane površine znašajo le 600 m², največje pa kar 144.819 m². Tudi zaradi teh velikih razhajanj v velikosti je primerljivost rezultatov med lokacijami problematična.

Nadaljnjo problematiko v primerjavo med rezultati obeh faz vnašajo razmerja med uporabo metod površinskega in podpovršinskega pregleda na lokacijah s prekrivanjem mrež obeh strategij (slika 4). Večina lokacij s prekrivanjem, tj. 157 (68 %), je bila v ekstenzivni fazi v celoti pregledana le s površinskim pregledom. Med temi jih je bilo v intenzivni fazi 126 (80 %) prav tako v celoti pregledanih površinsko, na 25 (16 %) lokacijah sta bili v intenzivni fazi uporabljeni obe metodi pregleda, na 6 (4 %) pa je bil v intenzivni fazi uporabljen le podpovršinski pregled. Sledi 56 (24 %) lokacij, na katerih sta bili v ekstenzivni fazi uporabljeni obe metodi pregleda. Med temi sta bili na 32 (57 %) obe metodi uporabljeni tudi v intenzivni fazi, na 17 (30 %) lokacijah le površinski pregled, na 7 (13 %) pa le podpovršinski pregled. Nadalje je bilo 19 (8 %) lokacij v ekstenzivni fazi pregledanih izključno podpovršinsko, v intenzivni fazi jih je bilo 17 (89 %) prav tako pregledanih le s podpovršinskim pregledom, 2 (11 %) lokaciji pa z uporabo obeh metod.

Poleg predstavljenih razmerij v primeru lokacij, na katerih sta bili v eni in/ali drugi fazi uporabljeni obe metodi pregleda, zadevo nadalje zapletejo razlike v deležu površinsko in podpovršinsko pregledane površine, ki med lokacijami močno variira. Pri 25 lokacijah, ki so bile v ekstenzivni fazi pregledane le površinsko, v intenzivni fazi pa z obema metodama, v slednji s kvartilnim razponom 53,5–90,5 %, povečini prevladuje površinski pregled (slika 5: A). Še bolj kompleksna so razmerja pri 56 lokacijah, ki so bile v ekstenzivni fazi pregledane z obema metodama. Med temi v ekstenzivni fazi s kvartilnim razponom 40,25–74,5 % prevladuje površinski pregled, vendar pa so razmerja precej enakomerno zastopana od skrajnosti skoraj povsem površinsko do skrajnosti skoraj povsem podpovršinsko pregledanih lokacij (slika 5: B). Med temi pa je na 32 lokacijah, ki so bile tudi v intenzivni fazi pregledane z obema metodama, v tej fazi razmerje nekoliko bolj izenačeno, z rahlo prevlado podpovršinsko pregledanih površin s kvartilnim razponom 32,25–73,25 % v primerjavi s površinsko pregledanimi površinami s kvartilnim razponom 26,75–67,75 % (slika 5: C). Na koncu naj omenimo še edini lokaciji, ki sta bili v ekstenzivni fazi pregledani izključno podpovršinsko,

v intenzivni fazi pa z obema metodama, pri čemer pa v obeh primerih s 87 % in 97 % izrazito prevladuje metoda podpovršinskega pregleda.

Vse opisane osnovne razlike, vezane na razmerja velikosti površin in razmerja metod pregleda, v primerjavo med rezultati ekstenzivne in intenzivne faze vnašajo kompleksnost, zaradi katere je lahko primerjava med obema fazama na posamezni lokaciji ter med njimi problematična. Temu lahko dodamo še za vsako lokacijo specifičen nabor dejavnikov, ki vplivajo na formacijske procese arheološkega zapisa, in nabor dejavnikov, ki vplivajo na njegovo zaznavanje v obeh fazah pregleda. Tako je vsaka lokacija specifičen splet okoliščin, ki bi zahteval podrobno samostojno obravnavo, zaradi česar so rezultati obeh faz pregleda na posamezni lokaciji in med njimi težko primerljivi. Kljub temu je potrebna splošna primerjava rezultatov, ki omogoča vpogled v določena splošna razmerja med rezultati ekstenzivnega in intenzivnega pregleda. Takšna primerjava namreč omogoča širši vpogled v splošne razlike v odkrivanju z obema strategijama pregleda ter nadaljnje razlike v odkrivanju med metodama površinskega in podpovršinskega pregleda.

Opis baze podatkov

Podatkovno zbirko sestavljata dve mapi s pripadajočimi datotekami:

□ 1_Tabela podatkov = Data table

- Slovar = Dictionary.docx: Datoteka s podrobnim opisom podatkov v tabelah podatkov.
- Tabela podatkov = Data table 1.xlsx: Tabela podatkov z vsemi lokacijami intenzivnega pregleda. Nekatera intenzivno pregledana območja se ne prekrivajo z ekstenzivno pregledanimi območji. Rezultati v tabeli so ločeni glede na površinski in podpovršinski pregled.
 - VSE = ALL: Tabela z vsemi lokacijami (n = 258), ki vsebuje podatke (1) o številu odkritih najdb posameznega obdobja, (2) o razmerjih med velikostjo ekstenzivno in intenzivno ter površinsko in podpovršinsko pregledanih površin, (3) o gostoti posameznih vrst gradiva, odkritih s površinskim in podpovršinskim pregledom, (4) o razmerjih med gostoto posameznih vrst gradiva,

odkritih v ekstenzivni in intenzivni fazi, ter (5) o regionalizaciji lokacij po Perko (1998).

- brez prekrivanja = no overlap: Tabela z lokacijami, kjer se ekstenzivni in intenzivni pregled ne prekrivata (n = 19).
- prekrivanje = overlap: Tabela z lokacijami, kjer se ekstenzivni in intenzivni pregled prekrivata (n = 232).

- Tabela podatkov = Data table 2.xlsx: Tabela podatkov z lokacijami pregleda, na katerih se ekstenzivni in intenzivni pregled prekrivata (n = 232). Rezultati površinskega in podpovršinskega pregleda so tokrat prikazani združeno. Poleg razmerij med površinami ekstenzivnega in intenzivnega pregleda so navedene površine v m².

□ 2_Analiza=Analysis

- Primerjava lokacij.pdf: Datoteka s podporno analizo primerjave rezultatov ekstenzivne in intenzivne faze pregledov, ki ni bila vključena v povezani izvorni znanstveni članek. Besedilo je samo v slovenščini.

Jezik baze podatkov: slovenski, angleški.

Vrste datotek: XLSX, DOCX, PDF

Lokacija baze podatkov

Repozitorij: Repozitorij Univerze v Ljubljani

Datum objave v repozitoriju: 19. 11. 2025

Trajnostni identifikator: PID20.500.12556/RUL-176053.

Vrednost in raba podatkov

Podatkovna baza na eni strani vsebuje podatke, ki so bili uporabljeni v primerjavi med rezultati ekstenzivnega in intenzivnega terenskega pregleda na avtocestah Slovenije ter namenjeni ovrednotenju učinkovitosti odkrivanja z ekstenzivnim površinskim in podpovršinskim pregledom ter intenzivnim podpovršinskim pregledom. S tem omogoča preverjanje rezultatov analize ter morebitne druge analize na podlagi istega niza podatkov. Na drugi strani pa so v podatkovno bazo vključeni tudi rezultati obsežnega dela analize, ki podpira rezultate, objavljene v Gruškovnjak 2025a.

Povezana dela in arhivi

Podatkovna zbirka je neposredno vezana na izvorni znanstveni članek (Gruškovnjak 2025a), posredno pa tudi na članke (Gruškovnjak 2022b, 2024a–b, 2025b).

Podatki o rezultatih terenskih raziskav temeljijo na originalni dokumentaciji terenskega dela, digitalnih podatkih in neobjavljenih poročilih, ki jih hranita Zavod za varstvo kulturne dediščine Slovenije (ZVKDS) in njegov Center za preventivno arheologijo (CPA) (glej Gruškovnjak 2022a).

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Data for comparing the results of extensive and intensive field surveys on Slovenian motorways

(Data paper)

Background

The database was created as part of doctoral research evaluating the effectiveness of archaeological field survey methodology in the specific environmental and cultural conditions of Slovenia (Gruškovnjak 2022a). Part of the research addressed the influence of survey methods and techniques, as well as artefact density, on the discovery of sites through field surveys. This led to the creation of the present collection, which consists of data obtained through a spatial comparison of the results of extensive and intensive surveys conducted along Slovenian motorways. Field research was conducted between 1994 and 2009 as part of the Slovenian motorway construction project, the largest development project in Slovenia to date (see Djurić 2003). Surface and subsurface field surveys were the primary methods used to detect previously unknown archaeological sites presumed to be located within the construction area.

On the one hand, the research was based on the finding that the effectiveness of site detection through field surveys is influenced by various factors, including the characteristics of the archaeological material and the methodology used to detect it (Gruškovnjak 2017a; 2019; Gruškovnjak, Tiefengraber, Črešnar 2019). On the other hand, it drew on the finding that data from intensively surveyed areas can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of less intensive survey strategies (Burger *et al.* 2004; Burger, Todd 2006, 241–243; Burger, Todd, Burnett 2008, 217–221; see also Banning *et al.* 2017). Within the framework of the motorway project, surveys were conducted in two phases – extensive and intensive – differing in survey intensity.

In this data paper, we present data obtained by comparing the spatial overlap of both phases of the survey, which were intended to analyse the influence of material density in the topsoil and the methodology of its detection, specifically survey intensity (extensive and intensive) and the survey method (surface and subsurface). The results of the analysis are presented in the research paper (Gruškovnjak 2025b), which is supplemented by this data paper, which provides a more detailed description of the data set used in the analysis. The collection includes tabular data on the locations where the two survey phases overlap, including the sizes of the surveyed areas, the number and density of finds, and other parameters considered in the analysis.

Geographical scope: Slovenia, Slovenian Hills, Drava Plain, Celje Basin, Ljubljana Basin, Dinaric lowlands and plateaus, Vipava Valley, Slovenian Istria.

Periods: Prehistory, Roman Period, Early Medieval Period, Modern Period (the field survey material is not dated more precisely).

Methodology

As part of the motorway project, the surface survey method was applied in unvegetated cultivated areas, while the subsurface survey method was used in vegetated uncultivated areas. Field research was conducted in two phases, extensive and intensive, which differ in survey technique and, above all, strategy. *Technique* refers to the manner in which the inspection method is carried out, while *strategy* refers to the spatial distribution of the technique's implementation (see Gruškovnjak 2017b, 116, note 50).

The extensive phase covered the entire motorway route and related structures. The survey strategy involved the use of collection units divided into 50m-long transects spaced 10m apart (Figure 1; see Gruškovnjak 2024a–b). The surface survey technique consisted of walking along the transects and collecting all surface finds detected within approximately 1 metre of the walking line. The subsurface survey technique involved excavating one test pit measuring 40 × 40 × 40cm on each transect and collecting the finds recovered from it.

Areas yielding positive results were identified as potential archaeological sites and subjected to the subsequent intensive survey phase. The survey strategy involved the use of a 10 × 10m quadrant grid (Figure 1; see Gruškovnjak 2024a–b). The surface survey technique involved examining the entire surface of each quadrant, while the subsurface survey technique involved excavating one test pit measuring 40 × 40 × 40cm in each quadrant (Djurić 2003, 16–18).

The results of the extensive and intensive surveys were subsequently processed using a geographic information system³. Unfortunately, data are not available for all locations where intensive surveys were conducted, partly due to the inaccessibility of some reports or incomplete data, and partly because time constraints prevented the acqui-

³ A database containing all the results of the surveys from both phases is currently being prepared.

sition and digitisation of data for all surveyed locations. In total, the results from 251 locations where intensive surveys were conducted were digitised. Of these, 19 locations show no spatial overlap between the grids of the two survey strategies.⁴ Consequently, data from 232 locations with spatially overlapping results from both survey strategies are available for analysis.

Data comparability

It should be noted that individual locations of intensive field surveys (hereinafter referred to as IFS locations) are not necessarily identical to individual locations determined on the basis of extensive surveys. Due to their size, some locations defined through extensive surveys were investigated using several spatially separated intensive survey grids. These grids therefore represent individual locations of overlap between the two survey strategies. Each grid was treated as a separate overlap location, as the comparison between the two survey phases requires the most continuous and narrowly defined overlap areas possible.

The number of IFS locations available here varies considerably by region (Figure 2) and does not correspond to the number of locations identified in the regions based on the extensive survey results. This discrepancy arises for several reasons: because data digitisation was not possible in some cases, because of a lack of overlap with the extensive survey, or because of differences in how locations were determined for the purpose of comparing the results of both survey phases.

Furthermore, it should be noted that comparing the results of both survey phases at overlapping locations is, to a certain extent, problematic. In almost no case is there a complete and exact overlap between the grids of the two strategies. The comparison therefore includes entire intensive survey grids that overlap completely or at least partially with the extensive survey grid, and extensive survey sampling units that overlap at least partially with them (Figure 1). As a result, the grids of both survey strategies may cover areas that the other does not. The size

ratios between extensively and intensively surveyed areas at individual overlap locations may therefore vary considerably (Figure 3: A). The greater the differences in area size, the more problematic their comparison becomes.

Most often, when comparing the total areas of both strategies, the extensive survey area accounts for 50–64% and the intensive survey area 36–50%. There are also significant differences in the absolute sizes of the intensively surveyed areas (Figure 3 B) and, consequently, in the sizes of the extensively surveyed areas included in the comparison. The quartile range of the size of intensively surveyed areas ranges from 3,958m² to 12,700m², with a median value of 7,000m², while the smallest intensively surveyed areas are only 600m² and the largest as much as 144,819m². Due to these significant size differences, the comparability of results across locations is problematic.

An additional complication in comparing the results of both phases arises from the ratio of surface to subsurface survey methods at locations where the grids of both strategies overlap (Figure 4). Most overlap locations, i.e. 157 (68%), were surveyed exclusively using surface survey during the extensive phase. Of these, 126 (80%) were also surveyed exclusively using the surface survey method in the intensive phase; 25 (16%) were surveyed using both survey methods in the intensive phase; and 6 (4%) were surveyed using only the subsurface survey method in the intensive phase.

This is followed by 56 locations (24%) where both survey methods were used in the extensive phase. During the intensive phase, both methods were used at 32 of these locations (57%); only surface survey at 17 (30%); and only subsurface survey at 7 (13%). A further 19 locations (8%) were surveyed exclusively by subsurface survey in the extensive phase, while in the intensive phase, 17 (89%) were also surveyed only by subsurface survey, and 2 locations (11%) were surveyed using both methods.

In addition to these ratios, further complexity arises at locations where both survey methods were used in one or both phases, owing to differences in the proportions of surface and subsurface survey areas. These proportions vary considerably between locations. At the 25 locations only surveyed using surface survey in the extensive phase and using both methods in the intensive phase, surface survey predominated at most of these sites, with a quartile range of 53.5–90.5% for the latter (Figure 5: A).

⁴ There are various reasons for this. Some locations are already known archaeological sites where there was no need for an intensive phase. Some represent areas of expansion of construction works that were not foreseen or known at the time of the extensive phase. Some represent areas where the intensive phase of the survey missed the area surveyed in the extensive phase.

The situation is even more complex at the 56 locations that were inspected using both methods in the extensive phase. At these locations, surface survey predominates in the extensive phase, with a quartile range of 40.25–74.5%, but the ratios are fairly evenly distributed from almost entirely surface-surveyed locations to almost entirely subsurface-surveyed locations (Figure 5: B). Among this group of 32 locations that were also surveyed using both methods during the intensive phase, the ratio is slightly more balanced. In this phase, subsurface survey shows a slight predominance of subsurface-inspected areas, with a quartile range of 32.25–73.25% compared to a quartile range of 26.75–67.75% for surface survey (Figure 5: C).

Finally, mention should be made of the two locations that were surveyed exclusively using subsurface survey in the extensive phase and with both methods in the intensive phase. In both cases, the subsurface survey method clearly predominated, accounting for 87% and 97% of the surveyed area, respectively.

All of the differences outlined above, relating to both area size ratios and the proportions of survey methods used, introduce complexity into the comparison of results from the extensive and intensive phases. This complexity makes direct comparison between the two phases at individual locations, as well as comparison between locations, problematic. In addition, each location is influenced by a specific set of factors affecting the formation of the archaeological record, as well as a set of factors influencing its detection in each survey phase. Each location therefore represents a unique combination of circumstances that would require detailed independent consideration, making it difficult to compare the results of both phases of the survey within a particular location and across locations.

Nevertheless, a general comparison of the results remains necessary in order to gain an insight into the general relationship between extensive and intensive survey outcomes. Such a comparison provides understanding of the general differences in detection between the two survey strategies, as well as of the differing contributions of surface and subsurface survey methods.

Database description

The database consists of two folders with associated files:

□ 1_Tabela podatkov = Data table

- Slovar = Dictionary.docx: A file containing a detailed description of the data in the data tables.
- Tabela podatkov = Data table 1.xlsx: Data table showing all locations of intensive surveys. Some intensively surveyed areas do not overlap with extensively surveyed areas. The results in the table are separated according to surface and subsurface surveys. The data are presented in three sheets:
 - VSE = ALL: Table with all locations (n=258), containing data (1) on the number of finds discovered in each period, (2) on the ratios between the size of extensively and intensively surveyed areas and those surveyed by surface and subsurface method, (3) on the densities of individual types of material discovered through surface and subsurface surveys, (4) on the ratios between the densities of individual types of material discovered in the extensive and intensive phases, (5) on the regionalisation of locations according to Perko (1998).
 - brez prekrivanja = no overlap: Table showing locations where extensive and intensive surveys do not overlap (n=19).
 - prekrivanje = overlap: Table showing locations where extensive and intensive surveys overlap (n=232).
- Tabela podatkov = Data table 2.xlsx: Data table with survey locations where extensive and intensive surveys overlap (n=232). The results of the surface and subsurface surveys are presented together in this report. In addition to the ratios between the areas of extensive and intensive surveys, the areas are also given in m².

□ 2_Analiza=Analysis

- Primerjava lokacij.pdf: File with supporting analysis comparing the results of the extensive and intensive survey phases, which was not included in the related research paper. The text is only in Slovenian.

Database language: Slovenian, English.

File types: XLSX, DOCX, PDF

Database location

Repository: Repository of the University of Ljubljana

Date of publication in the repository: 19/11/2025

Persistent identifier: PID 20.500.12556/RUL-176053.

Data value and reuse

On the one hand, the database presents data used in the comparison of results from extensive and intensive field surveys on Slovenian motorways, intended to evaluate the effectiveness of detection through extensive surface and subsurface surveys and intensive subsurface surveys. This allows verification of the analysis results, as well as any further analyses based on the same data set. On the other hand, the database also includes results from extensive analysis that support the results published in (Gruškovnjak 2025a).

Related works and archives

The database is directly linked to the original scientific article (Gruškovnjak 2025a) and indirectly to articles (Gruškovnjak 2022b, 2024a–b, 2025b).

The data on field research results are based on original fieldwork documentation, digital data, and unpublished reports stored by the Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia (IPCHS) and its Centre for Preventive Archaeology (CPA) (see Gruškovnjak 2022a).

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